

Studies in Oxidation-Reduction Potential. Part I. Cystine.

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The discovery of glutathione by Hopkins (*Biochem. J.*, 1921, 15, 286) in all living tissues and the probability of this substance acting as a carrier of oxygen has naturally directed the attention of investigators to the properties and behaviour of sulphhydryl bodies. Glutathione contains cysteine as one of its constituent parts and obviously the study of oxidation-reduction potential of cysteine has great significance in the study of tissue oxidation. Now, if the oxidation-reduction of cysteine according to the following scheme:—

were truly reversible, and a thermodynamic equilibrium existed at the noble electrodes, the value of electrode potential would be given by

$$-E = E_0 - \frac{RT}{F} p_{\text{H}} - \frac{RT}{F} \log \frac{[\text{cysteine}]}{\sqrt{[\text{cystine}]}}. \quad \dots (1)$$

Dixon and Quastel (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2943) and later on Michaelis and his co-workers (Michaelis and Flexner, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1928, 79, 689 ; Barron, Flexner and Michaelis, *ibid.*, 1929, 81, 743) have carefully studied the reduction potential developed by solutions of cysteine at gold and mercury electrodes and found the following equation to hold good.

$$E = E_0 - \frac{RT}{F} p_{\text{H}} - \frac{RT}{F} \log [\text{cysteine}]. \quad \dots (2)$$

Strangely enough they found that the addition of cystine has no influence on this electrode potential, and Barron, Flexner and Michaelis (*loc. cit.*) state "It is improper to speak of a cystine—cysteine system at a mercury electrode.....This system is not related to the problem of cysteine oxidation in metabolism."

This is a very unsatisfactory position, and further investigation appeared very desirable. The previous investigators brought a buffered solution of cysteine and cystine hydrochloride in contact with a noble metal under anaerobic conditions and the potential developed referred to the normal hydrogen electrode was found to be given by equation (2) where E_0 has the value -0.001 volt.

Now, if the potential is due to the oxidation of cysteine, it ought to be of the same order of magnitude as is necessary for the reduction of cystine. This point could be tested by determining the overvoltage at the cathode necessary for the reduction. Table I gives the potential we have found to be necessary for the reduction of cystine.

The experimental arrangement consisted of two glass beakers containing the same solution of cystine hydrochloride connected by means of a siphon. One beaker contained ring-shaped anode of platinum gauze and the other a large piece of platinum, silver, copper foil or mercury as cathode. A stirrer rapidly stirred the liquid at the cathode and the overvoltage was determined by means of a Wolff potentiometer against a decinormal calomel electrode.

The cystine and cysteine in the cathode liquid was estimated colorimetrically according to Folin and Marenzi (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1929, 83, 108) with slight modification. 4 C.c. of the cathode liquid was pipetted out and transferred to a 100 c.c. volumetric flask and 2 c.c. of a standard solution of cystine (containing 1 mg. per c.c. in *N*-sulphuric acid) to another 2 c.c. of a freshly prepared 20 p.c. solution of sodium sulphite was added to the standard cystine solution for its reduction and allowed to stand for a minute. 18 C.c. of 20 p.c. sodium carbonate was then added to each flask. After the addition of carbonate solution, 2 c.c. of 20 p.c. lithium sulphate was added to each flask and finally 8 c.c. of uric acid reagent was added to each flask with shaking. In the case of the standard, the solution was made up to a definite volume with a freshly prepared 3 p.c. solution of sodium sulphite, and with deaerated water in the other case. The strength was then determined colorimetrically.

TABLE I.

p_{H} .	Current density.	Electrode.	Cathode potential against <i>N</i> -hydrogen Electrode.	Extent of reduction.
3.2	1.46×10^{-4}	Mercury	-0.7588	Measurable in 3 hrs
"	2.09×10^{-4}	"	-0.7696	Complete in 3 hrs.
"	3.20×10^{-4}	Copper	-0.4441	Very small in 3 hrs.
"	3.84×10^{-4}	"	-0.4442	47.06% in 3 hrs.
"	"	"	-0.4445	70.2% in $6\frac{1}{2}$ hrs.
"	3.13×10^{-4}	Silver	-0.4407	49.4% in 3 hrs.
"	"	"	-0.4489	86.96% in 3 hrs.
"	5.20×10^{-4}	Platinum	-0.3520	None in 3 hrs.
"	"	"	"	None in 6 hrs.
"	1.04×10^{-3}	"	-0.4205	22.4% in $3\frac{1}{2}$ hrs.
"	7.81×10^{-4}	"	-0.4086	24% in 5 hrs.
"	"	"	-0.4186	39.2% in $7\frac{1}{2}$ hrs.
7.0	1.98×10^{-4}	Mercury	-0.9109	Complete in 3 hrs.

It is well known that the direct method used above and the commutator method advocated by Newbury, give different over voltage values. The former method gives invariably higher values. There is at the present time no unanimity of opinion as to which method gives the correct value. The data in Table I have therefore no quantitative significance. One important fact however should be noted; on a platinum surface, hydrogen discharged at current density 1×10^{-3} can reduce cystine to cysteine. at p_{H} 0.3, but not at lower densities. It is clear that the cystine-cysteine potential cannot be far removed from that of the potential developed in a hydrogen gas cell.

While the investigation was in progress two papers (Williams and Drissen (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1930, **87**, 441) and the other by Fischer, (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1930, **89**, 753) were published in which the problem has been treated differently. Cysteine was oxidised to cystine by oxidising agents (I_2 , KIO_3 , $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ etc.) and attempts were made

to locate the redox potential by electrometric titration. The normal potential varied from +.415 to +.548 volt depending on the oxidising agents. A positive potential at the cathode of the observed magnitude should certainly be incapable of reducing cystine to cysteine. Williams and Drissen consider that in the electrometric titrations, one minute was sufficient for the attainment of equilibrium. This assumption is perhaps not correct, and what they actually recorded, may, for example in the case of iodine as oxidising agent, be the 'redox' potential of the system $I_2 \rightleftharpoons 2I'$, the actual value of the potential depending on the concentrations of the I' ion and the small concentrations of I_2 that may exist in the solution at the end of one minute.

From the qualitative knowledge of the negative potential necessary for the reduction of cystine to cysteine, a method for finding out accurately the redox potential was worked out as follows:

Under perfectly anaerobic conditions, cystine was partly converted to cysteine by cathodic reduction at a mercury electrode. The electrolysing current was then switched off, and the negative potential determined from time to time while a current of nitrogen was continually flowing. Under these conditions, we would expect to observe a limiting value of the potential corresponding to the cystine-cysteine redox system. This expectation was realised when the p_H value was 7 and more. For lower p_H values erratic results were obtained. It is remarkable that the limiting values of the *E.M.F.* observed for p_H values 7 or more are capable of being expressed by equation (1) where E_0 is found to have the value 0.0793.

Also for the same p_H , the variation in the *E.M.F.* with changes in the cystine-cysteine ratio follows the relation—

$$E_1 - E_2 = RT/F \log \frac{[\text{cysteine}]_1 \sqrt{[\text{cystine}]_2}}{\sqrt{[\text{cystine}]_1} [\text{cysteine}]_2} \quad \dots (3)$$

$E_1 - E_2$ is not given by the following relation

$$E_1 - E_2 = RT/F \log [\text{cysteine}]_1 / [\text{cysteine}]_2 \quad \dots (4)$$

as demanded by the equation of Dixon and Quastel.

In solutions of a substance like cystine, the slightest trace of oxygen has a great effect on the potential. The most important

feature of the experimental technique was therefore to remove the oxygen as completely as possible from the cystine-cystine mixture. This involved the supply of carefully purified nitrogen and an efficiently sealed apparatus. Nitrogen prepared from ammonium chloride and sodium nitrite was stored up in a jar and further purified by allowing it to flow up a tower packed with copper turnings which were kept moist throughout with a mixture of equal volumes of saturated ammonium carbonate solution and liquor ammonia (*d* 0.93). The issuing gas was then passed successively through three towers containing

FIG. 1.

alkaline pyrogallate solution, dilute sulphuric acid solution and concentrated sulphuric acid respectively. A piece of white phosphorus did not glow in the issuing gas showing that the oxygen pressure was less than 0.0007 mm. This gas was finally allowed to enter the cell. All connections from the gas reservoir to the cell were made of glass tubing. The cell was made out of a glass bottle of suitable size and had a

capacity of about 150 c.c. This was fitted with a rubber stopper in which six holes were bored at equal distances from one another. The following glass tubes were inserted in the bores for the purpose mentioned below:—

(i) A is the nitrogen inlet with a ground-glass joint. The lower end of the tube nearly touches the surface of mercury inside the cell.

(ii) F is the nitrogen outlet. Its outer end dips in water to serve as a trap.

(iii) B is a glass tube at the lower end of which is fused a platinum wire in order to make an electrical connection with the mercury within the cell. Enough mercury should be taken within the cell to immerse the wire completely.

(iv) C is a stop-cock large enough to allow the passage of a 2 c.c. pipette. This was used for the introduction of the solution within the cell as well as for withdrawal of solution from the cell for analysis.

(v) E is a siphon-tube with two stop-cocks H and I for making liquid connection with the anode chamber. The stop-cock I is on the main body of the siphon and is of considerable diameter so that it offers only a small resistance. When the electrolysing current is switched off, the stop-cock is also closed in order to prevent any back rush of the liquid from the anode chamber to the cathode chamber where obviously the pressure will fall due to the bubbling of nitrogen at a slower rate.

(vi) D is an arrangement for making connection with the decinormal calomel electrode. It is filled up with saturated potassium chloride.

G is the anode chamber. The anode used is a platinum gauze ring. A wire resistance was inserted between the poles of a battery of cells and the required voltage for electrolysis was applied by tapping off the current from the resistance. The cell fitted as stated above was made airtight with marine glue, soft sealing wax and a final coating of paraffin wax. It was then completely immersed in a bath of liquid paraffin in order to exclude the last traces of air from entering. The nitrogen reservoir was connected at the ground glass part of A and a decinormal calomel electrode was connected at D. A regular stream of nitrogen helped to stir the liquid.

The hydrogen-ion concentration was kept practically constant by means of buffer solutions; the cystine-cysteine ratio was varied by continual reduction at the cathode under perfectly anaerobic conditions for different lengths of time.

Cystine, dissolved in the least quantity of hydrochloric acid was added to the buffer solution to bring it to the desired concentration. Due to the addition of hydrochloric acid in the cystine solution, the the p_H value of the buffer solution was diminished by about 0.6 units every time. The p_H value of cystine solution in each case was therefore determined electrometrically.*

Cystine solution thus prepared was introduced into the electrolytic cell and a portion of it into the anode chamber. The potentials were measured against a 0.1N—calomel electrode. While the reduction was in progress, the nitrogen was bubbled more rapidly

* The value of p_H obtained electrometrically may not be absolutely correct as cystine react as a powerful reducing agent. As a matter of fact, however, the colorimetric method gave values of p_H similar to those obtained by the electrometric method. For the verification of reaction (4) the absolute value of p_H is not also essential.

to secure an efficient stirring. But after switching off the current, the potential was read with the nitrogen passing slowly and at an approximately regular rate through the electrolytic cell. Small variations in the rate of bubbling are without effect on the steady *E.M.F.*

After the attainment of the steady state, more cystine was reduced electrolytically (5 milliamperes for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour) as before, and the measurements continued. After each reduction, 2 c.c. of the cathode solution was taken out and the amount of cystine in the mixture determined colorimetrically.

Pfansteil's C. P. cystine was purified by dissolving several times in very dilute caustic soda solution and then precipitating with dilute acetic acid. 2 C.c. of the cystine solution was added to 80 c.c. buffer solution to bring it to the desired concentration.

Mercury used as cathode was carefully purified. All experiments

FIG. 2.

were done at 25° and when the experiment was over, sulphuretted hydrogen was passed through the cathode liquid, but it failed to produce any precipitate showing that in the cathode no complex of cystine and mercury had been formed.

Table II shows the limiting potentials in volts referred to the normal hydrogen electrode for p_H values above 7. Fig. 2 illustrates the rate of establishment of the steady potential.

The values of the steady *E.M.F.* observed by us are somewhat different from the values of the electrode potential observed by Michaelis on a mercury surface exposed to a solution of cysteine in absence of oxygen.

pH.	Mol. conc. of cysteine.	Mol. conc. of cysteine.	TABLE II		$E_1 - E_2$		
			E_1	E_2	Obs.	Calc. from (5)	Calc. from (6)
8.60 (1)	.0024	.0090	-.3458	.0800	.0557	.0556	0.0842
8.60 (2)	.0045	.0076	-.4015	.0803			
8.50 (1)	.0024	.0090	-.3510	.0801	.0104	.0111	.0078
8.50 (2)	.0018	.0040	-.3614	.0801			
8.40 (1)	.0024	.0018	-.3331	.0783	.0258	.0245	.0185
8.40 (2)	.0015	.0037	-.3587	.0784			
8.05 (1)	.0018	.0013	-.3060	.0906	.0322	.0316	0.223
8.05 (2)	.00087	.0031	-.3391	.0792			
7.5 (1)	.0034	.00084	-.2541	.0807	.0235	.0220	.0195
7.5 (2)	.0028	.0018	-.2776	.0792			

2.303 RT/F = 0.069 at 25°

Discussion.

It will be seen from Table II that in neutral and in alkaline solutions the electrode potentials obtained at a mercury surface by the partial reduction of cysteine *in situ* is due to a reversible transformation according to the following scheme.

In acid solutions, however, the results are not capable of being expressed by any rational thermodynamic equation.

This behaviour can be correlated with the electrochemical and biochemical behaviour of cysteine and glutathione. Cannan and Knight (*Biochem. J.*, 1927, 21, 1389) consider that the cation of cysteine hydrochloride should be regarded as an acid dissociating three hydrogen ions thus :—

The respective dissociation constants are 1.4×10^{-2} , 7.3×10^{-9} , and 4.6×10^{-11} . Between p_H 3 and p_H 7 cysteine exists almost entirely as a neutral internal salt molecule

III and IV increases. Below p_H 7 the thiol groups (-SH) in cysteine (CSH) is stable but above this value the thiol group dissociates into $\text{S}^- + \text{H}^+$. It is in this region, when such dissociation becomes possible, that we should expect the thiol group to be an active reducing agent in a reversible transformation thus

The work of Hopkins (*Biochem. J.*, 1925, 19, 787) on the oxidation of fats and proteins by glutathione also brings out clearly the characteristic differences in the oxidation by thiol groups in acid and alkaline range. Thus in conformity with the investigations of Meyerhof (*Pflüger's Archiv*, 1923, 199, 531), Hopkins found that in acid range the oxidation of unsaturated fatty acids by oxygen of the air is catalytically accelerated by substances containing the thiol (SH) group. The thiol group forms with oxygen a peroxide $(\text{RSH})_2\text{O}_2$ which completely transfers the oxygen to the acceptor fatty acid resulting in regeneration of the thiol group. In alkaline range however, 'the (SH) group is so freely oxidisable that unless its concentration in the system be relatively high, it rapidly disappears even in the presence of fatty acids'. In this region of p_H we are dealing with an induced reaction, the inductor thiol compound and the acceptor fatty acid being both oxidised in the process. This difference in behaviour

can be explained by the hypothesis that in the formation of disulphide from two thiol molecules, the first stage consists in the dissociation of the thiol (SH) group into $\text{S}^- + \text{H}^+$. In the region of p_{H} where this dissociation is possible, oxidation of the thiol into the disulphide occurs. For the values of p_{H} below this range, a thiol compound is stable in the sense that it is incapable of forming a disulphide.

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Received December 21, 1932.